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3 **Iron-dependent, non-enzymatic processes promoted by *Phaeomoniella***
4 ***chlamydospora* and *Phaeoacremonium aleophilum*, agents of esca in**
5 **grapevine**

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9

10 **Abstract.** Esca is a serious disease associated primarily with two fungi, *Phaeomoniella*
11 *chlamydospora* and *Phaeoacremonium aleophilum*. An examination of the cellulolytic
12 system of fungi showed that iron interacts with the metabolic activity of the fungi,
13 enhancing their pathogenic potential in a manner complementing the pathogenic activity of
14 the enzymes they produce. Iron enables the fungi to break down the crystalline cellulose,
15 making up for the lack of a specific enzyme to do this, while it does not affect the activity
16 of other enzymes present, such as endoglucanase. Some of the implications of iron on both
17 the wood and leaf symptoms of esca are discussed.

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20 **Key words:** siderophores, ferric iron, ferrous iron, hydroxyl radicals, cellulose
21 degradation, phytotoxins.

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Abbreviations: CBS, Centraalbureau voor Schimmelcultures; PDA, Potato Dextrose Agar; ANOVA Analysis of Variance; CAS Chrome Azurol S (CAS); PIPES, piperazine-1,4-bis(2-ethane sulphonic acid) free acid; CMC Carboxymethylcellulose sodium salt; HDTMA hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide; F_{sp} , specific fluidity; T_b , efflux time of buffer solution; T_p , efflux time of polysaccharide solution; g, gravity; OD optical density; $\Delta A(A_{532})$, difference between the absorbance of the treatment at a given iron concentration and the absorbance of the same treatment without iron

1 **1. Introduction**

2

3 Esca is a serious disease of grapevine wood with a complex aetiology. It is found in
4 almost all areas where vines are cultivated. In its chronic form esca causes losses in yield
5 and reduces the longevity of the vines [1].

6 Two systemic fungi, *Phaeoconiella chlamydospora* (W. Gams, Crous, M.J. Wingf. &
7 Mugnai) Crous & W. Gams and *Phaeoacremonium aleophilum* W. Gams, Crous, M.J.
8 Wingf. & Mugnai, cause at least three of the syndromes of the esca complex: dark wood
9 streaking of the rooted cuttings, Petri disease, and esca proper in the vineyard [2]. The esca
10 proper syndrome is characterised essentially by brown wood streaking in the trunks and
11 main branches, and by chlorotic and necrotic stripes or spots on the leaves (the so-called
12 tiger stripes).

13 The leaf symptoms of esca do not recur regularly every growing season, and their
14 recurrence, or failure to do so, cannot be predicted. Their onset of leaf symptoms is
15 presumably due to the fungi acting at a distance since the leaves are not attacked directly
16 by them [1,3]. In mature vineyards esca is often associated, at least in the Mediterranean
17 area, with white rot of the wood, which is another syndrome of the esca complex, and
18 which is caused mainly by the basidiomycete *Fomitiporia mediterranea* M. Fischer [2].

19 The mechanisms of the disease process and the characteristics of the systemic fungi
20 that cause esca have been the subject of much research over the last few years.

21 Both fungi colonise the vine wood, probably at least in part because they produce
22 pectinolytic enzymes [4] and xylanases that attack the hemicelluloses [5]. In the
23 considerable enzymatic activity that occurs in growing colonies of *P. chlamydospora* and
24 *P. aleophilum*, *P. aleophilum* is more effective than *P. chlamydospora* in attacking the
25 phenolic compounds because of the phenoloxidases, catalases, tannases and probably also

1 the laccases it produces [5-8]. Lastly the cellulolytic system is incomplete since both
2 fungi lack the enzymes that attack crystalline cellulose [6].

3 Studies have also been carried out to examine how *P. chlamydospora* and *P.*
4 *aleophilum* cause esca symptoms and interfere with the normal functioning of the wood
5 and the leaves. These studies have concerned 1. alterations in xylem functions [9-10]; 2.
6 the melanin formed by *P. chlamydospora* or *P. aleophilum* as a consequence of their
7 interaction with grapevine [11]; 3. the production of phytotoxins such as scytalone and
8 isosclerone that appear to interfere with the physiological processes of the leaves and with
9 the onset of the leaf symptoms [11-14]; 4. variations in the levels of iron in symptomatic
10 leaves; these variations are probably related to pathogenic effects of the fungi [15-16].

11 Iron seems to have an important role in the physiology of the fungi, in the interaction
12 between the fungi and the vine host, and particularly in the mechanisms that involve the
13 reactive oxygen species, including the hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$). In the first stages of wood
14 decay caused by dark rot agents such as *Gloeophyllum trabeum*, iron is involved in the
15 production of hydroxyl radicals through the Fenton reaction, described [17] as follows:

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17
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19 In their turn, the $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals are involved in many processes relating to both the
20 pathogenetic activity of the fungi and the vine defence mechanisms. These processes
21 involving $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals can be related to the pathogenic mechanisms already mentioned, to
22 the detoxification of wood polymers, including the polyphenols protecting the vine from
23 disease [18], and to the rapid production of reactive oxygen species, known as oxidative
24 burst, with which the plants respond to pathogen attack, and more generally to stresses
25 [19].

1 The present study, building upon preliminary indications that iron has a role in the
2 infections caused by esca fungi [15], is intended to further understanding of the complex
3 interaction between *P. chlamydospora*, *P. aleophilum* and the vine host during the process
4 of infection. Specifically, biological tests in the laboratory were employed to study the role
5 that iron has in promoting non-enzymatic mechanisms, with the production of radicals by
6 the tracheomycotic fungi. A possible correlation of these radicals with the formation of leaf
7 symptoms or the development of esca-related necrosis in vinewood is discussed.

8

9 **2. Materials and methods**

10

11 *2.1. Fungal strains*

12

13 *Phaeomoniella chlamydospora* strain CBS 222.95 and *Phaeoacremonium aleophilum*
14 strain CBS 631.94 (Centraalbureau voor Schimmelcultures, Utrecht, The Netherlands)
15 from esca-infected vines were used in the tests. The fungi were cultured on potato dextrose
16 agar (PDA; Difco Laboratories, Detroit, MI, USA) in the dark at a thermostat-controlled
17 temperature of $20\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$.

18 Inoculum for the tests consisted of a plug of agar+mycelium, removed with a 6-mm
19 diameter cork borer from the edge of a two-week-old colony.

20

21 *2.2. Culture media*

22

23 To study the effect of iron on the mycelium growth of *P. chlamydospora* and *P.*
24 *aleophilum*, and to assess siderophore production, the fungi were cultured on a saline
25 solution described by Highley [20], except that it did not contain any iron. In 1 l of solution
26 were dissolved: 2 g ammonium nitrate, 2 g monobasic potassium phosphate, 0.5 g

1 magnesium sulphate heptahydrate, 0.1 g calcium chloride, 0.57 mg boric acid, 0.31 mg
2 zinc sulphate heptahydrate, 0.039 mg copper sulphate pentahydrate, 0.036 mg manganese
3 chloride tetrahydrate, and 0.018 mg ammonium molybdate tetrahydrate. To the saline
4 solution was added 15 g l⁻¹ agar, after which it was sterilised in an autoclave at 121°C for
5 25 min. The medium was chilled and amended with a sterile solution of glucose to reach
6 the final glucose concentration of 5 g l⁻¹, thiamine hydrochloride and streptomycin
7 sulphate. Iron for the tests was added as described below.

8 The occurrence of ferrous iron in the culture medium was determined in the liquid
9 medium derived from the saline solution mentioned above, which was also used to
10 examine the degradation of carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) and of crystalline cellulose, and
11 the formation of hydroxyl radicals. A plug of agar+*P. aleophilum* or agar+*P.*
12 *chlamydospora* mycelium (sterile agar for the control) were cultured in test tubes each
13 containing 20 ml of liquid medium. The iron in the form of ferric sulphate hydrate, titre 21-
14 23% of iron (Carlo Erba, Milan, Italy) was added to the sterilised medium to reach final
15 iron concentrations of 1, 10 and 100 mg l⁻¹ (control: water without iron). The carbon
16 source was chosen depending on the assay, as described below.

17

18 2.3. *Mycelium growth at different iron concentrations*

19

20 Iron was added to the medium in the form of ferric sulphate hydrate to reach the
21 concentrations above mentioned. The medium was placed in 90 mm Petri dishes (20 ml per
22 dish) and cooled before placing a plug of mycelium agar in the centre of each dish. The
23 treatments containing only iron, and the control without mycelium or iron received only
24 sterile agar. Fungal colonies were incubated in darkness in a growth chamber at a
25 temperature of 25±2° C and the growth of each colony and of each Petri dish was
26 monitored at two-day intervals by measuring the orthogonal diameters. Measurements

1 were expressed as the average diameter achieved by the colony depending on the time
2 elapsed since inoculation of the medium. Treatments were replicated five times, each
3 replicate consisting of one Petri dish. For each fungus and inspection date, the average
4 diameter of colonies grown at different ferric concentrations were compared using SAS
5 Procedure ANOVA followed by mean separation using Fisher's LSD test at $P = 0.05$ in
6 SAS (SAS Institute, Cary, NC, USA).

7

8 2.4. *Chrome Azurol S assay*

9

10 Siderophore production was qualitatively determined with the Chrome Azurol S (CAS)
11 assay, carried out on an agarised medium as described by Fekete [21]. With this test the
12 medium is initially dark-blue, and orange halos around the growing fungal colonies
13 indicate the occurrence of siderophores produced by the fungus.

14 The medium for the test was prepared as follows. A solution containing piperazine-1,4-
15 bis(2-ethane sulphonic acid), free acid (PIPES) was prepared by adding 30.24 g of PIPES
16 to make up 900 ml of Higley's saline solution minus iron. The pH was adjusted to 6.8 with
17 NaOH 50% w/v before adding 15 g agar. The solution was sterilised by autoclaving and
18 cooled. Glucose (5 g l^{-1} final), streptomycin sulphate and thiamine hydrochloride were then
19 added to the solution. Separately, an acid solution of iron, CAS and
20 hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (HDTMA) was prepared by dissolving 60.5 mg of
21 CAS into 50 ml water and mixing with 10 ml of ferric solution (1 mM FeCl_3 , 10 mM HCl),
22 and 40 ml of 72.9 mg HDTMA aqueous solution. After sterilisation, the solutions, one of
23 which contained PIPES and the other CAS, iron and HDTMA, were mixed in a ration of
24 9:1 to obtain the final substrate.

25 The distribution of the medium to the Petri dishes, the inoculation of the fungi, the
26 cultivation conditions, and the replicates were as described above. Siderophore production

1 was monitored by inspecting the Petri dishes every day until the orange halo appeared. The
2 test was carried out three times. Results were expressed as the mean of the experiments,
3 and the standard error (SE) of the means were calculated.

4

5 2.5. *Ferrozine assay*

6

7 Concurrently with the CAS assay, the ferrozine assay described by Pierson and Clark
8 [22] was carried out to determine the occurrence of ferrous iron in the growth medium of
9 *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum* through the formation of a chromogenic complex
10 between ferrozine and ferrous iron. Preliminary trials indicated that the optimal time for
11 the ferrozine assay was about 10 days after the orange halo first appeared in the CAS
12 assay.

13 For the ferrozine assay, 1 ml of the medium (containing 5 g l⁻¹ of glucose as the carbon
14 source) in which *P. chlamydospora* or *P. aleophilum* had been grown at 0, 1, 10 and 100
15 mg ml⁻¹ ferric iron was collected from the test tube and passed through a Whatman 4 filter
16 to remove all mycelial structures (control: sterile medium). One hundred µl of the filtrate
17 was mixed with an equal volume of an acid solution prepared as follows: 5.14 g of
18 ferrozine was dissolved in 100 ml water; 500 ml of concentrated HCl was added, the
19 solution was cooled and brought to 1 litre with double distilled water. Then 750 µl of
20 double-distilled water was added to the mixture. The solution was incubated at 98°C for 10
21 min in a water bath and then cooled down to room temperature, after which 100 µl of
22 ammonium acetate buffer was added containing 800 g l⁻¹ of ammonium acetate and 700 ml
23 l⁻¹ of ammonia 4.0 M. The formation of a chromogenic complex in the solution was
24 assessed spectrophotometrically by measuring A(A₅₆₂) with a two-channel Jasco V-530
25 spectrophotometer equipped with a UV/VIS lamp (Jasco Europe Srl, Cremella, Lecco,
26 Italy). A calibration curve was obtained by measuring the absorbance A(A₅₆₂) of gradual

1 dilutions of ferrous iron (100, 50, 25, 12.5 and 6.25 mg l⁻¹ of iron) prepared concurrently
2 with the sample.

3 The concentration of ferrous iron in a sample was determined from the calibration
4 curve and expressed as mg l⁻¹.

5 The experiment was performed twice with three replicates per treatment, each
6 consisting of one test tube. Means of separate experiments were expressed with SE. For
7 each ferric iron concentration, the concentrations of ferrous iron of the *P. chlamydospora*
8 growth medium, the *P. aleophilum* growth medium, and sterile agar were analysed by
9 ANOVA using SAS, and means were separated using Fisher's LSD at P = 0.05.

10

11 2.6. *Viscosimetric assay*

12

13 The degradation of CMC was determined with a viscosimetric assay [23] in liquid
14 cultures of *P. chlamydospora* or *P. aleophilum*, or in cultures without fungus at 0, 1, 10 or
15 100 mg l⁻¹ ferric iron.

16 The test was carried out in the dark, in liquid medium containing 5 g l⁻¹ CMC as the
17 carbon source. Ten ml of growth medium was removed from the test tube 60 days after
18 inoculation and centrifuged at 1500 g for 5 min. The supernatant was transferred to another
19 tube and the absence of fungal structures was verified under the light microscope.

20 Subsequently 5 ml of the sample was loaded on a capillary G20 Jena Glass tube immersed
21 in a water bath (Thermo Boy-MGW; Lauda DR. R Wobser GMBH, Lauda-Königshofen,
22 Germany) at 24.9±0.1°C as measured with a Hanna HI 90.63 thermometer (Hanna
23 Instruments, Padua, Italy). The constant k of the capillary tube under these conditions was
24 calculated as a function of the efflux time (in sec) of 5 ml of distilled water and was on
25 average 68.5 sec.

1 The efflux times of the buffer solution and of the solution of each sample containing
2 the polysaccharide were recorded and expressed as specific fluidity according to the
3 formula: $F_{sp} = T_b/T_p$ where T_b is the efflux time of buffer solution and T_p is the efflux time
4 of polysaccharide solution [23] and the specific fluidity is therefore dimensionless. In our
5 case the buffer consisted of Higley's saline solution minus iron and the efflux time was on
6 average 70 sec, with 97.9% of the fluidity of distilled water. The efflux time was measured
7 five times on each aliquot, each aliquot coming from one replicate. The experiment was
8 performed twice with three replicates per treatment, each consisting of one test culture
9 tube. Means of separate experiments were expressed with SE. The specific fluidity of the
10 *P. chlamydospora* growth medium, the *P. aleophilum* growth medium, and sterile medium
11 for each iron concentration was subjected to ANOVA analysis using SAS, followed by
12 mean separation using Fisher's LSD at $P = 0.05$.

13

14 2.7. Thin layer chromatography assay

15

16 Degradation of crystalline cellulose was determined by means of TLC as described by
17 Michalowski et al. [24]. Crystalline cellulose at a rate of 5 g l^{-1} was added as a carbon
18 source to the culture medium containing 0, 1, 10 or 100 mg ml^{-1} ferric iron. The cellulose
19 was insoluble in water and formed in the test tube a visible bottom on which a plug of
20 agar+*P. aleophilum* or agar+*P. chlamydospora* mycelium was placed. The controls
21 received a plug of sterile agar.

22 About 60 days after inoculation the samples were separated by TLC. One ml of culture
23 medium was removed from the test tube and centrifuged for 5 min at 1500 g . The
24 supernatant ($20 \mu\text{l}$) was spotted on flexible TLC plates covered with silica gel (Baker,
25 Phillipsbourg, NJ, USA) in a 1.5 cm wells 1 cm apart and 1 cm from the edge of the plate,
26 and developed three time employing a butanol, ethanol, water $5:5:5 \text{ v:v:v}$. The sugars

1 cellobiose, cellotriose, cellotetraose and cellopentose were used as standards for each plate
2 at a concentration of 1 mg l^{-1} . When the separation was completed, the carbohydrates were
3 visualised with a mixture of 4 g diphenylamine, 4 ml aniline and 20 ml phosphoric acid in
4 200 ml acetone. The coloured plate was then subjected to densitometry to determine any
5 peaks and the distance of these peaks from the starting point of migration. The degradation
6 products were recognised by comparing the migration distance of the peaks generated by
7 the samples from the start of the run with the corresponding distances of the peaks
8 generated by the standards loaded on the same plate.

9 Data were expressed as chromatograms of the migration area of the oligosaccharides
10 (11-15 cm from the start of the chromatographic run). The chromatograms of the four
11 standard sugars run on different lanes of the same plate are shown in one figure.

12

13 2.8. *Deoxyribose assay*

14

15 Production of the hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$) was assessed by determining the degradation
16 undergone by 2-deoxy-D-ribose using the method of Aruoma [25], modified for the
17 absence of ascorbic acid so that the ascorbic acid would not interfere with the capacity of
18 the fungi to reduce ferric iron. The 2-deoxy-D-ribose at the rate of 5 g l^{-1} was added as the
19 only carbon source to a culture medium containing 0, 1, 10 or 100 mg ml^{-1} ferric iron, in
20 which *P. chlamydospora* or *P. aleophilum* had been grown for 60 days. For the controls the
21 2-deoxy-D-ribose was added to sterile medium containing the same iron concentrations.
22 The test tube containing the medium was shaken and an aliquot of 2 ml was removed and
23 passed through cheese cloth. The absence of fungal structures in the filtrate was verified
24 under a light microscope. An aliquot of 1.2 ml of filtrate was added to 1 ml of 1%
25 thiobarbituric acid (w:v) dissolved in 50 mM NaOH and 1 ml of 2.8% trichloroacetic acid
26 (w/v). The solution was heated to 80°C for 30 min and left to cool. The sample thus

1 obtained was transferred to a spectrophotometric cuvette to measure the $A(A_{532})$ against
2 blank without fungi and iron.

3 The data were calculated as the difference $\Delta A(A_{532})$ between the absorbance of the
4 treatment at a given iron concentration and the absorbance of the same treatment without
5 iron. The experiment was carried out twice with three replicates per treatment, each
6 consisting of one test tube. Means of separate experiments were expressed with SE. The
7 absorbance values of the fungi and of the sterile control when the iron concentration was
8 the same in both, and when there was no iron were analysed by ANOVA using SAS and
9 means separated using Fisher's LSD at $P = 0.05$.

10

11 **3. Results**

12

13 *3.1. Mycelium growth at different iron concentrations*

14

15 Mycelium growth of *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum* colonies was statistically the
16 same ($P>0.05$) with all iron concentrations tested (1-100 mg l⁻¹), and also with the controls
17 without iron. Only *P. aleophilum* showed two measurements when mycelium growth was
18 slightly less than that of all the other test groups, at day 17 from inoculation, and then only
19 with an iron concentration of 100 mg l⁻¹ (Fig. 1). Colony shape and mycelium appearance
20 never showed any differences.

21 **FIGURE 1**

22

23 *3.2. Chrome Azurol S assay*

24

25 The orange halo indicating the formation of siderophores by the fungi appeared around
26 both *P. aleophilum* and *P. chlamydospora* colonies (Table 1). With *P. aleophilum* the halo

1 appeared on average 9 days after inoculation on the agar medium containing the CAS
2 reagent, whereas with *P. chlamydospora* the halo appeared somewhat later, on average 15
3 days after inoculation.

4 **TABLE 1**

5

6 *3.3. Ferrozine assay*

7

8 The formation of ferrous iron in the liquid culture media is shown in Fig. 2. Both fungi
9 significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased levels of Fe^{2+} , compared with test groups that initially
10 had the same concentration of Fe^{3+} but did not contain the fungi. *P. aleophilum* grown with
11 initial Fe^{3+} concentrations of 1, 10 and 100 mg l^{-1} showed Fe^{2+} concentrations of
12 respectively 2.8, 12.5 and 19.0 mg l^{-1} , which were much higher than the Fe^{2+}
13 concentrations for all the other test groups. When comparing the same initial iron
14 concentrations between *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum*, *P. chlamydospora* had a
15 pattern that was similar but always lower than that of *P. aleophilum*, 2.3, 7.9 and 14.4 mg l^{-1}
16 with 1, 10 and 100 mg l^{-1} of iron respectively. These differences were significant for the
17 highest iron concentrations ($P < 0.05$).

18 **FIGURE 2**

19

20 *3.4. Viscosimetric assay*

21

22 The results of the viscosimetric tests on the degradation of CMC are shown in Table 2.
23 The addition of iron to the culture medium in no case significantly ($P > 0.05$) changed
24 viscosimetric activity. When only CMC was added, the specific fluidity of the medium was
25 reduced to 0.337, giving an average specific fluidity of 0.354 with the different iron
26 concentrations (1, 10, 100 mg l^{-1}). The addition of *P. chlamydospora* to the culture medium

1 containing CMC increased the specific fluidity of the medium to 0.52, which was
2 significantly higher than that of the medium without a fungus and lower than that of the
3 medium with *P. aleophilum* ($P < 0.05$). When iron was added to the *P. chlamydospora*
4 cultures the specific fluidity did not change significantly ($P > 0.05$) compared with the
5 culture containing *P. chlamydospora* alone, varying from a minimum of 0.51 to a
6 maximum of 0.53. The *P. aleophilum* growth medium containing CMC but not iron had a
7 high specific fluidity at 0.908, indicating that the CMC had been almost completely broken
8 down. The specific fluidity was greater than that with the *P. aleophilum* medium and with
9 the media not containing any fungi ($P < 0.05$). Here too, adding iron to the medium did not
10 significantly increase the specific fluidity ($P > 0.05$).

11 **TABLE 2**

12

13 3.5. *Thin layer chromatography assay*

14

15 The chromatographic assay on the culture media without fungi, and with or without
16 iron, revealed that degradation products were never produced by crystalline cellulose (Fig.
17 3b-e). When *P. chlamydospora* was grown on a liquid medium containing 10 mg l⁻¹ of
18 iron, the chromatograms indicated that cellobiose was formed (Fig. 3i). The *P.*
19 *chlamydospora* medium plus iron at 100 mg l⁻¹ led to the formation of various sugars, two
20 of which corresponded to cellobiose and cellotetraose (Fig. 3j). In the *P. aleophilum*
21 medium, the degradation of crystalline cellulose was visible only with an iron
22 concentration of 100 mg l⁻¹. Unlike the *P. chlamydospora* growth medium, the *P.*
23 *aleophilum* growth medium had a broad and composite peak in the degradation area, which
24 revealed that degradation had occurred, but did not clearly indicate which sugars had been
25 involved. The peak achieved with the *P. chlamydospora* growth medium was also lower
26 than with the *P. aleophilum* growth medium (Fig. 3o).

1 **FIGURE 3** The Figures 3 a b c d e should be positioned one above the other. The same
2 sequence should be arranged for the Figures 3 f g h i j and the Figures 3 k l m n o. The
3 three sequences (as left, middle and right column) should compose the final Figure (see
4 pag 29).

5
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7 3.6. Deoxyribose assay

8

9 The formation of hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$) was evaluated by a spectrophotometric test
10 that exploited the capacity of the radicals to break down 2-deoxy-D-ribose to products that
11 were in their turn transformed into chromogenic compounds endowed with a maximum
12 absorbance at 532 nm (A_{532}) after a reaction with thiobarbituric acid. Results are shown in
13 Fig. 4.

14 The presence of iron in the medium without the fungi slightly increased absorbance to
15 a maximum of 14.3 mOD, recorded with the highest initial iron concentration of 100 mg l⁻¹
16 ¹. In a medium containing iron, *P. aleophilum* and *P. chlamydospora* showed a dose-
17 response effect that was particularly evident with iron at a concentration of 100 mg l⁻¹,
18 where the ΔA_{532} values were 147.2 mOD for *P. chlamydospora* and 1127.5 mOD for *P.*
19 *aleophilum*, which differed significantly ($P < 0.05$). In general, degradation products in a
20 medium in which *P. chlamydospora* had been grown were always greater in quantity than
21 they were in a *P. aleophilum* medium or in a medium without any fungi ($P < 0.05$),
22 irrespective of the concentration of iron present in the medium. A *P. aleophilum* medium
23 however always had a significantly greater effect than a medium not containing fungi ($P <$
24 0.05).

25 **FIGURE 4**

26

1 4. Discussion

2

3 The role of *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum* in the symptoms of esca is thought to
4 be related to the capacity of these fungi to colonise the vascular tissues of the host vine and
5 to produce phytotoxins. This belief has been buttressed by recent studies, which have
6 however made it clear that the situation is more complex and still not entirely elucidated,
7 inasmuch as it also involves environmental factors and/or factors relating to the physiology
8 of the vines [26-27].

9 The present work has found that *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum* promote non-
10 enzymatic mechanisms that may be involved in esca disease processes, leading to the
11 formation of both the inner symptoms, dark wood streaking, and the external tiger stripes
12 on the leaves.

13 The growth patterns and shape of the colonies of the two fungi were not affected by the
14 presence of iron in the medium. However, *P. aleophilum* was more sensitive than *P.*
15 *chlamydospora* to iron in the medium, and began producing siderophores sooner; both of
16 these characteristics are typical of fungi that grow in the presence of low concentrations of
17 iron [28].

18 Culture medium not containing the fungi formed Fe^{2+} especially at the higher Fe^{3+}
19 concentrations tested (10 and 100 mg l^{-1}) but the amount of Fe^{2+} that formed was not
20 correlated with the amount of Fe^{3+} added to the medium. It can therefore be excluded that
21 the increase in Fe^{2+} was caused by a dose-response effect; most likely it was due to the two
22 forms of iron reaching a spontaneous equilibrium.

23 The greater concentration of Fe^{2+} in the medium containing Fe^{3+} in which *P.*
24 *chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum* were grown can be explained by assuming that the fungi
25 chelate and reduce the iron by means of siderophores that they produce, thus making the
26 iron available for their metabolism and in their surroundings. Another possible explanation

1 of the greater concentration of Fe^{2+} in the growth medium is that the melanins are also
2 involved; these compounds were reported to form in vine wood inoculated with *P.*
3 *chlamydospora* or *P. aleophilum* [29]. The melanins may have contributed to create a
4 reducing environment because of their electron transfer properties and this would have
5 favoured the formation and maintenance of Fe^{2+} in the culture medium [30].

6 In previous studies of the enzymes produced by *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum*,
7 it was shown that these fungi were able to break down CMC, indicating that they produced
8 endoglucanase, but not the more complex celluloses including crystalline cellulose [6]. The
9 present study likewise found that *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum* broke down CMC
10 irrespective of the occurrence of iron in the medium, but above all it was shown that both
11 fungi broke down crystalline cellulose only in the presence of iron. It can therefore be
12 postulated that the iron caused *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum* to activate
13 mechanisms that complemented their enzyme activity, and that this made them more
14 aggressive against vine tissues. The existence of such mechanisms is confirmed,
15 particularly for *P. chlamydospora*, by the fact that, as shown in the chromatograms, the
16 fungi grown with iron at 100 mg l^{-1} displayed peaks corresponding to the polysaccharides,
17 with an even number of β -glucoside residues (cellobiose and cellotetraose), which have
18 been associated with the intervention of endoglucanase [24]. The participation of iron in
19 the degradation of crystalline cellulose by *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum* without
20 their particular enzymatic activity suggests that the Fenton reaction was activated here,
21 which caused the oxidation of the previously formed Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} and consequently the
22 formation of the $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals [31]. In such a mechanism, the radical first attacks the
23 crystalline cellulose, and then the endoglucanases become active. Moreover, *P.*
24 *chlamydospora* broke down crystalline cellulose to the oligosaccharides more rapidly than
25 did *P. aleophilum*, even though the viscosimetric tests indicated that *P. chlamydospora* had

1 lower levels of endoglucanase, suggesting that for *P. chlamydospora* the non-enzymatic
2 way correlated with iron was more important.

3 The production of the radical was further confirmed by the 2-deoxy-D-ribose assay,
4 which demonstrated that non-enzymatic oxidative processes occurred that ultimately
5 produced •OH. The formation of radicals was assessed at 60 days. Under these conditions,
6 this assay has a good dose-response pattern, and it distinguishes the activity of the one
7 fungus from that of the other. Specifically, *P. chlamydospora* produced more radicals than
8 *P. aleophilum*, confirming what was found with the degradation of crystalline cellulose.
9 The results obtained overall suggested that *P. chlamydospora* relied more on non-
10 enzymatic mechanisms than did *P. aleophilum*, probably to compensate for its having less
11 enzyme activity than *P. aleophilum*, as was found in earlier studies [5-7] and because, as
12 Larignon found [32], *P. chlamydospora* is not able to break down *in vivo* the cellulose of
13 the cell walls of esca-infected vines.

14 It seems likely that each of the two fungi therefore has its own multiple pathogenic
15 mechanism that on the one hand involves enzyme activity, and on the other oxidative
16 activity promoted by *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum* differently depending on the
17 different ways in which they metabolise iron. The involvement of oxygen radicals
18 promoted by *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum* in the esca infective process can be
19 explained differently depending on the ability of these radicals to interfere with the
20 metabolism of the vines or the fungi [17,33].

21 Amalfitano et al. [34] carried out chemical tests that led them to postulate that
22 polyphenols occurring in esca-affected vinewood could help neutralise reactive oxygen
23 species. The oxidative processes promoted by the fungi and demonstrated in this work
24 could therefore help explain the increase in polyphenol levels recorded in symptomatic
25 vines: they are a reaction of the vines to the formation of hydroxyl radicals.

1 Romero-Martinez et al. [35] found that the ascomycete *Sporothrix schenckii* is
2 protected from the oxygen radicals by the melanins. These melanins would be produced by
3 oxidative processes of derivatives of scytalone, at the expense of isosclerone formation
4 [36], following a scheme that was proposed for *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum* by
5 Buno and Sparapano [11]. According to this scheme, conditions particularly favouring the
6 re-oxidation of iron and the formation of hydroxyl radicals and the melanins would lower
7 the availability of scytalone and isosclerone to form the leaf symptoms [14]. Leaf
8 symptoms did indeed seem to be reduced in preliminary trials in which iron was applied to
9 the soil in order to limit esca in the field [16].

10 Further studies are in progress to investigate more fully the role of phytotoxins
11 produced by the tracheomycotic fungi. One of these studies suggests that scytalone and
12 isosclerone, as associated with the formation of the melanins, are involved in the wood
13 discoloration caused by *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum* (Surico, unpublished data).
14 The hydroxyl radicals, which as this work has shown are formed by *P. chlamydospora* and
15 *P. aleophilum*, may have a role in the discoloration of infected wood, by causing the
16 melanins to form.

17 In conclusion, this work has shown the existence of non-enzymatic mechanisms
18 promoted by *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum*, and this may change the view taken of
19 how the tracheomycotic fungi of esca interact with the processes of wood decay and leaf
20 symptoms.

21

22

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9

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- 17

1 **Figure legends**

2

3 **Figure 1.** Growth of colonies of *P. chlamydospora* and *P. aleophilum* when Fe³⁺ was
4 added to the growth medium for 25 days, at the following concentrations: 0 mg l⁻¹
5 (—); 1 mg ml⁻¹(- -); 10 mg ml⁻¹ (- - -); 100 mg ml⁻¹ (- - -). The means from
6 treatments at each inspection date did not differ statistically ($P > 0.05$) according to
7 Fisher's LSD.

8

9 **Figure 2.** Concentration of Fe²⁺ assessed in the growth medium without fungi (black
10 histograms), *P. chlamydospora* growth medium (white histograms), and *P. aleophilum*
11 growth medium (chequered histograms). Data represent the mean of two independent
12 experiments, and error bars indicate the standard error (SE). Different letters above the
13 histograms for each Fe³⁺ concentration indicate significant differences ($P = 0.05$)
14 according to Fisher's LSD.

15

16 **Figure 3.** Thin layer chromatography analysis of the oligosaccharides accumulation in
17 sterile medium (left), *P. chlamydospora* (middle), *P. aleophilum* (right) at different iron
18 concentrations. In the chromatograms of standard oligosaccharides (a, f, k) the numbers
19 above the peaks (2, 3, 4, 5) indicate the number of β -glucoside residues that characterise
20 the oligosaccharide for that peak, that are cellobiose, cellotriose, cellotetraose and
21 cellopentose, respectively; sterile medium (b), *P. chlamydospora* (g), *P. aleophilum* (l)
22 without iron; sterile medium (c), *P. chlamydospora* (h), *P. aleophilum* (m) with 1 mg l⁻¹
23 iron; sterile medium without iron (d), *P. chlamydospora* (i), *P. aleophilum* (n) with 10 mg
24 l⁻¹ iron; sterile medium (e), *P. chlamydospora* (j), *P. aleophilum* (o) with 100 mg l⁻¹ iron.

25

1 **Figure 4.** Spectrophotometric analysis for the degradation of 2-deoxy-D-deoxyribose in
2 the culture medium without fungi (black histograms), *P. chlamydospora* growth medium
3 (white histograms), and *P. aleophilum* growth medium (chequered histograms).
4 Absorbance was measured at 532 nm. Data represent the mean of two independent
5 experiments, and error bars indicate the standard error (SE). For each of the three Fe³⁺
6 concentrations, different letters above the histograms indicate significant differences
7 according to Fisher's LSD ($P = 0.05$).
8

1 **Table 1.** Chrome Azurol S (CAS) test. Production of siderophores by colonies of
2 *Phaeoaniella chlamydospora* and *Phaeoacremonium aleophilum* grown in Higley
3 medium.

4

Test group	Time of appearance of orange halo	
	Days after inoculation ^a	SE ^b
Sterile control	-	-
<i>P. chlamydospora</i>	15	2
<i>P. aleophilum</i>	9	3

5

6 ^aThe value of the time of orange halo appearance represents the mean of three experiments.

7 ^bSE was calculated from three experiments.

8

9

1 **Table 2.** Specific fluidity of liquid culture medium containing carboxymethylcellulose
 2 (CMC) inoculated with a plug of agar+*Phaeoconiella chlamydospora* mycelium, a plug
 3 of agar+*Phaeoacremonium. aleophilum* mycelium, or a sterile plug.

Treatment	Specific fluidity ^a			
	Ferric iron (mg l ⁻¹)			
	0	1	10	100
<i>P. chlamydospora</i>	0.503a (±0.027) ^b	0.497a (±0.030)	0.500a (±0.041)	0.504a (±0.025)
<i>P. aleophilum</i>	0.893b (±0.040)	0.886b (±0.051)	0.893b (±0.037)	0.891b (±0.062)
Sterile agar	0.336c (±0.063)	0.335c (±0.040)	0.336c (±0.027)	0.336c (±0.042)

5
 6 ^aValues represent the means of two separate experiments ± SE.
 7 ^bValues in each column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P =
 8 0.05, whereas values in the same row did not differ significantly (*P*>0.05) according to
 9 Fisher's LSD.

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3 [Figure 1](#)

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2 [Figure 2](#)

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6 **Figure 3**

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2 **Figure 4**
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